

Deployment of Traffic Light and Vehicle Devices for Routing Applications

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Abstract—Routing of vehicles is an important procedure, whereby there is the necessity to reach a destination in a timely manner. As such, networking of vehicles is undertaken using wireless and telecommunication capabilities, in order to promote such a service. In this paper, we present two subsystems, namely a vehicle and a traffic light subsystem aiming to interconnect them, in order to provide a routing service in a distributed manner. We show the deployment of the traffic light and vehicle subsystem in a real world application and we provide results on the capturing and counting of vehicles, the acquisition of the GPS signal of the vehicles as well as their speed. The aforementioned metrics reach a dedicated server. Finally, we employ an electric vehicle, which we use to visit a set of customers and we utilise an off-the-shelf GPS logger to obtain metrics such as speed and location. The aim is to show its applicability, when we are going to employ it with our built subsystem, for future work.

Index Terms—traffic light, vehicle, routing, network, antenna, device, electric vehicle, GPS

I. INTRODUCTION

The idea behind interconnecting vehicles and creating a network that will take advantage of information from the vehicles themselves, such as the vehicle's GPS coordinates, speed, accelerator pedal position, number of brakes, acceleration and has its roots in the Internet of Things (IoT) [1]. The general philosophy of the IoT is to connect all electronic devices to a local area network or to the Internet.

The networking of vehicles, therefore the creation of a Vehicular Ad-hoc Network (VANET) is one of the most important technologies and through it a variety of applications can be implemented that concern all these vehicles, road traffic, even drivers, passengers and pedestrians. Such applications also belong to the field of Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS), whose main purpose is the monitoring and management of road traffic. A VANET is used to exchange messages from Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V) as well as from vehicles to other Road Side Units (RSUs) or Vehicle to Infrastructure (V2I), and even to exchange messages from Vehicles to networked mobile

devices, Pedestrian (V2P) [2]. In general, this communication is often called V2X, i.e. vehicle communication with all the interconnected devices in the network that we define.

Communication between devices in a VANET is usually done with technologies and protocols [3] such as the following:

- Zigbee
- 5G
- 4G-LTE
- IEEE 802.11 (Wi-Fi)
- IEEE 802.11p
- Bluetooth

Because the amount of information from networked vehicles, devices that are likely to be on traffic lights and moving pedestrians increases linearly as the networked devices increase and in combination with the potentially low computing power of the devices used, data processing is often done with Edge techniques, or Fog computing [4], [5], where many network devices contribute to data processing.

The capabilities of VANET are a very topical issue that is being researched and constantly expanded. A very important aspect of a VANET is the safety services offered to both drivers and passengers of vehicles and pedestrians i.e., warnings of cross-collisions, lane changes, overtaking, frontal collisions, vehicle damages, emergency, wrong lane driving, traffic signal violation [6]. In addition, VANET focus on efficient traffic management aiming to reduce fuel consumption and environmental pollution [7]. These services could:

- Exchange information using Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) communications
- Provide a more efficient driving experience.
- Improve traffic flows.
- Reduce congestion on the road network.
- Display information about distance traveled, average speed, average fuel consumption, temperature.

- Provide estimations about the cost of a trip, the remaining drivable fuel quantity and distance.
- Provide information about unexpected events on the road network

Optimal routing of vehicles in order to arrive faster at their destination and therefore to avoid as much traffic congestion as possible is the primary concern of this paper. We take onboard the model described in [8] whereby routing takes place in a dynamic manner in wireless networks. There is also an application in the literature that has applied this research work to vehicular networks [9]. The main contribution is the rapid sight of change in the traffic conditions and the notification of the server, whereby weights are calculated, in order to navigate the vehicle towards the fastest road to its destination. Note that the maturity of this system will provide real time information to the vehicle directly and it will decide its next route in a decentralised manner.

The motivation of this work lies in the development of a network of traffic light devices that will measure the speeds of vehicles in order to update routing engines such as the Open Source Routing Machine (OSRM) [10]. The OSRM updates the speed of each road in the form of a graph edge. Our intention is to calculate the backpressure weights of the route towards a destination and its alternative and obtain the respective speeds of the vehicles in order to feed them to the routing engine. This may be used for emergency vehicles as well, where first responders will have to navigate to a specific place in a fast manner.

We describe the deployment of devices presented in [11] to an area in Thessaloniki, whereby the vehicles are counted to obtain queues and the vehicles transmit speeds to calculate respective weights that are the primary index for the routing of the vehicles. The contributions of this paper are twofold. Initially, we give results of the deployed devices and secondly, we employ an electric vehicle to a real world scenario, visiting a number of customers and we obtain metrics of the journey such as the distance, speed and energy consumption. Essentially, in this paper we are describing experience of deployment of real world devices and real world applications.

The contributions of this paper are the following:

- We present the RSU units and the vehicle device that have been implemented.
- We provide information regarding the experimental setup of such devices to the area of Thessaloniki.
- We give results regarding the RSUs' operation in detecting vehicles and counting them.
- We provide results of the counting and the speed acquisition from the vehicles.
- We provide initial results a real world application of an electric vehicle reaching a number of customers, with the purpose of using the vehicle system.

The remainder of this paper is as follows: section II gives the system model, section III gives the subsystems description, section IV describes the installation of the traffic light subsystems, section V gives the results of the subsystems

deployment, section VI provides a description of a real world application of visiting customers scenario using an electric vehicle and section VII gives the conclusions and future work.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a network of roads where routing decisions are undertaken in a distributed fashion at every traffic light change. Hence, we consider a queue in every road where traffic is bidirectional. To this end, we utilize the backpressure model to make the decisions about the next route of every vehicle.

As described in [12] in the backpressure model, every road has a queue of vehicles. We denote the vehicles as d that are available on road i . Let $Q_i^{(d)}(t)$ be the current amount of cars in road i , which is called the queue backlog. The road queue backlog from one traffic light change slot to the next, satisfies;

$$Q_i^{(d)}(t+1) \leq \max[Q_i^{(d)}(t) - \sum_{b=1}^N \mu_{ib}^{(d)}(t), 0] + \sum_{a=1}^N \mu_{ai}^{(d)}(t) + A_i^{(d)}(t) \quad (1)$$

For all $i \in 1, \dots, N$ such as $i \neq d$. In this equation $A_i^{(d)}(t)$ corresponds to the cars d that arrive to road i in the traffic light change slot t . Furthermore, $\mu_{ib}^{(d)}(t)$ is the car forwarding rate on car linking roads (i, b) on time t . Equivalently, the denotation follows for $\mu_{ai}^{(d)}(t)$. Moreover, $\sum_{a=1}^N \mu_{ai}^{(d)}(t)$ may be greater than the arrivals of cars to the road i on time traffic light change slot t . Hence, we have an inequality in (1), since we may have limited backlog in road a .

The Backpressure model operates in a distributed manner to determine the routes of the vehicle. However, for simplicity in this work we send queues of the vehicles to a server and in conjunction with the speed and location we can calculate the weight as

$$w_{i,j} = (\Delta Q_{i,j} - \tau \theta_{i,j}) \overline{R}_{i,j} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta Q_{i,j} = Q_i - Q_j$ is the queue backpressure and Q_i, Q_j are the backlogs of junctions i, j respectively, \overline{R} is the road car driving rate and $\theta_{i,j}$ a road traversal penalty that depends upon the particulars of the utility. The parameter τ is a constant trades system queue occupancy for minimizing the penalty. This is a proven mathematically sound formulation that has been successfully applied to practical implementations of wireless networks and proposed for road networks.

III. SUBSYSTEMS DESCRIPTION

In this section we provide the reader with a brief description of the subsystems utilised for the counting and routing of the vehicles, namely the vehicles and the traffic lights subsystem. The full description of these subsystems are given in [11].

A. Vehicles Subsystem

The structure of the subsystem (Fig. 1) consists of an Arduino Uno [13] which functions as the central processing unit, the Fona 808 transceiver [14] which enables GSM and GPRS connection as well as the possibility of obtaining GPS

Fig. 1: Vehicle Subsystem

Fig. 2: Traffic Lights Subsystem

position, through suitable GPS and GSM antennas. Equally important functionality with the acquisition of GPS position is the connection to the electronic brain of the vehicle. For this reason, hardware [15] was used that allows the Arduino to connect via USB and control various types of connections, such as the OBD connection of a vehicle. The ELM327 cable [16] was also used for this purpose as an OBD-II reader, which essentially connects the subsystem to the vehicle. The appropriate power supplies were used to meet the needs of the system and there is a sufficient margin for the possible future addition of additional hardware.

B. Traffic Lights Subsystem

It consists of an Arduino Uno and two environmental sensors PM2.5 and carbon dioxide [17], [18], the Fona 808 component, the Raspberry Pi 3 Model B + [19], the appropriate GSM and GPS antennas and the PiCam v2 camera. In this case, too, the appropriate power supplies were used to adequately meet the electricity needs. The Raspberry Pi therefore counts and receives from the camera the number of vehicles passing as well as their direction and speeds. At the same time, the Arduino takes the environmental measurements and sends them to Raspberry. The above data is sent by Raspberry to the host server and is necessary for the operation of the routing algorithm. The device can be seen in Fig. (2).

C. System Operation

The traffic light devices receive the vehicle data, ie their number, their speeds and their direction as well as the environmental data and send them to the central server. The method for vehicle identification is the Mixture of Gaussians Background Subtraction [20]. The vehicle devices send GPS coordinates as well as other information from vehicle electronic brains. The host server now has all the necessary data and in this way calculates the weights for the Backpressure algorithm to work. The host server sends the weights to the Open Source Routing Machine (OSRM) server [21], in turn

the OSRM calculates the optimal path and sends it to the requested vehicle. Of course, if the vehicle is stopped at a traffic light, the algorithm checks if the optimal path has changed and if so, sends the new route to the user.

To count the speeds we use the conversion of the real coordinates to the coordinates of the camera and use the vehicle identification to produce the final speed. Because we can not know from the beginning the inclination and the general perspective of the traffic light subsystem, after the installation of the subsystem, we measure the physical distances from one end of the image produced by the camera to the other and do this for both dimensions. Note that potential distortion of the camera image is not considered and left for future work. For example, if the image of the camera is defined by Cartesian coordinates x, y , and we have measured that the x -axis has a natural length of 12m, then we can proceed to the next step. We know from the beginning that the image we produce is 400x300pixels, so we can directly say that,

$$1\text{pixel} = \frac{12}{400} = 0.03\text{m} \quad (3)$$

We also know how many frames per second (FPS) our subsystem processes, a number that changes dynamically. If we identify and count the vehicles, at the time of counting we see the processing FPS, even 10FPS and therefore the time mediated between the two frames is,

$$\frac{1}{10} = 0.1\text{sec} \quad (4)$$

We also find how many pixels the center of the vehicle has moved from frame to frame, let it be 5 pixels, and finally the speed of the vehicle is given by the following formula,

$$\text{speed} = \frac{0.03 * 5}{0.1} * \frac{3600}{1000} = 5.4\text{km/h} \quad (5)$$

If, depending on the position y of the vehicle, the physical distance on the x -axis changes, which is reasonable and

may occur due to the inclination of the respective traffic light subsystem, then the implementation changes slightly. Depending on the position y in which the vehicle is identified, we find the physical distance of the two ends of the camera on the x -axis and then the same process continues. This distance is initially found by linear interpolation, assuming that there is a linear relationship. We therefore find the line $x = a * y + b$ having measured at different points y the physical distance x and then we can use this line to calculate x and therefore following the above procedure we find the velocity.

IV. INSTALLATION OF TRAFFIC LIGHT SUBSYSTEM

In order to successfully build our system, an access point was required to be installed close to the traffic light subsystems.

A. AccessPoint

The Nanobeam Airmax NBE-M5-19 antennas were used [22] for Internet access of traffic light subsystems. Because internet access in many places is not guaranteed, their use in conjunction with Raspberry's wired or wireless internet capability introduces access to it anywhere. The general rationale is therefore to use an antenna that acts as an access point and then each traffic light subsystem to be equipped with an antenna of the same type that will wirelessly pick up the signal from the access point, after of course the proper connection between the antennas. The antenna was powered by an Ethernet cable from the Power over Ethernet (PoE) which was integrated into the subsystem just for this purpose and from the PoE, an Ethernet cable powers the Raspberry with the signal from the antenna connection.

The orientation of the first antenna that functions as an access point was very important (Fig. 3). Although the installation points of these subsystems are very close to the Center for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) and therefore the access point, the orientation of the antenna that functions as an access point was chosen to be in the area of Themi (close to Thessaloniki) in order to expand the system there as well. The above is not restrictive, as the antennas of the subsystems can be oriented directly in such a way that there is a connection between them and the access point.

Between CERTH and Themi, there is a hill, which limits the line of sight (line of sight) and therefore attenuates the signal to a great extent. The orientation was therefore made in such a way that the lower half of the Fresnel zone is lost due to the ground, while the upper part is not obstructed. The ultimate goal is to be able from some point in the area of Themi to be able to install an antenna that will receive the signal from the access point of the technology park and then with an Ethernet cable will be connected an additional antenna that will act as a second point and will provide the desired signal to subsystems in Themi.

B. Traffic Light Subsystems

Here we describe the installation of a single device, namely the device with ID: 8. The points selected were the two

Fig. 3: Access Point Antenna

intermediates, ie a traffic light and a lighting pole. The procedure to be done on the day of installation was as follows:

- Subsystem support.
- Antenna support and orientation.
- Connect the antenna to the Ethernet cable while waiting.
- Power supply to the subsystem.
- Check for proper operation

The first subsystem was installed using a ladder, at the traffic light at the intersection, oriented towards Themi. The power supply was made safely from a traffic light cable which was not used.

The appropriate processes were performed on the electrical panel and an automaton was installed for the exclusive management of the subsystem. Fig. 4 shows the final result of the installation. It is worth noting that for the control of the subsystem, an antenna of the same type was set up outside a vehicle we used for the process, oriented to the access point to CERTH, through which we had access to a laptop and the internet and the private network. The use of an additional web application that displays real-time video from the camera was used, the proper orientation of the device was checked.

C. Network Configuration

Before installing the subsystems, we first prepared the network so that when installing a traffic light subsystem and the

Fig. 4: Traffic Light Subsystem Installation

corresponding antenna, the connection to the access point is made directly and the device operates, without any additional intervention. So we created an internal private network, in which our devices have static private IP addresses.

Both in Raspberry, which is the backbone of the traffic light subsystems and in the antennas, the above process is quite simple and is done through the appropriate graphical interface of Raspberry and antennas. From this point the appropriate settings were made at the access point so that the network could operate successfully. More specifically, at the access point to CERTH, after consultation with the administration center, a static public address IP was given. For maximum security, incoming and outgoing traffic for this address was only allowed on certain ports.

We thus set up a private network that can operate autonomously each time, with minor changes to the settings so that it adapts to an access point. From the Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the antennas we setup network settings. This process is extremely important because it allows the final system to operate in accordance with the specifications we have explained so far but also introduces the possibility of secure remote management of subsystems and all antennas. The above, was an important factor for the installation, as at any time there was access to either the access point, or the traffic light subsystem or its antenna. Remote management achieves the greatest possible security, as access to individual devices and antennas is done with strong codes and is allowed only through the access point, where the appropriate port direction rules must be defined. For example, we can define the following rule:

- If IP (access point) is accessed.
- From a specific authorized IP (IP we accept).
- At a specific door.
- Then forwarded access to a specific private IP.

- And at a specific door.

In this way, during the installation process we could directly after the proper orientation of the antenna and power supply to the device, check the operation of the installed subsystem and give the appropriate inclination and orientation for the best possible operation of identification and counting vehicles.

V. RESULTS

The results of this section show the efficiency in the vehicle counting as well as a description of the vehicle tracking algorithm.

A. Vehicle Counting

Figs 5 (a) and (b) show the counting of vehicles from device 8, after its installation. In these images, the blue line counts the vehicles heading upwards, ie towards Thermi, while the orange line counts the vehicles heading downwards, ie towards CERTH. With the proper programming method, we exclude all vehicles coming from the left and right of the intersection. However, the possibility remains to count the vehicles coming from both the right and the left of the intersection.

After installing the subsystem with ID: 8, it was deemed necessary to install another one in the lighting pillar mentioned above with a different viewing angle to compare results, in order to determine the best possible geometric settings for optimal vehicle counting with the method followed.

So, then we proceeded to install the subsystem with ID: 7. The same procedure was followed, only this time the power supply came from a cable from an underground channel that was dug exclusively for the subsystem, observing all the necessary protection measures. In addition, a bucket vehicle was used to mount the subsystem.

It is worth noting that at the end of both the previous and this installation, a hole was made in the protection tube of the external Ethernet cable from the subsystems to their antennas, in order to prevent the accumulation of moisture inside. Fig. 6 (a) and (b), show the result of the counting by the subsystem with ID: 7, after its installation.

After the completion of the installation of the traffic light subsystems, we proceeded to measure the physical dimensions of the optics from the cameras so that we could proceed to the counting of the speeds. Figs 6 (c) show the procedure performed for the measurement concerning the traffic light subsystem with ID: 7 with the horizontal dimensions. Note that an equivalent procedure was performed for the vertical dimensions as well.

After measuring the physical dimensions, we added to the subsystems the ability to measure the speeds of passing vehicles. This function, in combination with the counting of vehicles, is important for the calculation of weights and therefore for the optimal routing.

In Figs 7 and 8 the reader can see the vehicle counting from the subsystem with ID = 7 as well as the speeds of the passing vehicles. Note that the colour corresponds to the colour of the line in previous figures showing the vehicles from one direction. The opposite direction of the passing vehicles is available and it is omitted for space constraints.

(a) Vehicles Count from subsystem 8 - 2

(c) Vehicles Count from subsystem 8 - 2

Fig. 5: Vehicles Count from subsystem 8

(a) Vehicles Count from subsystem 7

(a) Vehicles Count from subsystem 7

(c) Vehicles Count with dimensions

Fig. 6: Vehicles Count with horizontal dimensions

B. Vehicle Tracking Application

For the vehicle tracking application performed by the traffic light subsystem with ID: 4, the following steps were required:

- Construction of a virtual polygon that has limits on the boundaries of the road section in which the camera sees.
- Implementation of a point detection algorithm in a polygon.
- Add a label to the vehicle according to its coordinates.

Therefore, specifically for the subsystem with ID: 4 we found the GPS coordinates at four ends of the image as captured by the camera and then constructed the corresponding polygon. The four yellow dots that define this polygon in this case are shown in Fig. 9.

In the image above the labels are random and await the entry into the polygon of a vehicle having a vehicle subsystem. It is worth mentioning that the distances of the vertices of the polygon are not Euclidean but distances of a large circle. The above fact, however, does not introduce restrictions in this scenario as the vertices are very close to each other and therefore the error we get using the Euclidean distance is very small. This is because at such short distances the curvature

of the earth is very small. The above procedure can be generalized for all subsystems and thus there is the possibility to implement this functionality throughout the system.

VI. EXPERIENCE IN REAL-WORLD APPLICATION USING AN ELECTRIC VEHICLE

A pilot application has been deployed in the area of Thessaloniki city in an attempt to capture the processes followed by a company offering transport services to other businesses utilizing a technologically advanced system as the proposed in practice. Note that we used an off-the-shelf GPS logger, in order to provide the reader with initial results regarding our approach. The aim is to utilize the vehicles subsystem in future experiments. It is a B2B real-world application in which a technical assessment and an operational evaluation have been conducted in order to identify advantages and possible drawbacks. The data set contains 35 corporate customers (10) and the majority of customers are located in the city center even though there are some customers in remote areas (such as Chortiatis, Melissochori, Pentalofos, etc.).

The operational constraints are:

Fig. 7: Vehicles Counting Subsystem ID=7

Fig. 8: Vehicles Speed Subsystem ID=7

- Given a homogeneous fleet of depot-returning capacitated vehicles, the goal is to design a set of vehicle routes in order to satisfy the delivery requirements of a set of customers. The depot is the premises of the transport company depicted in blue Fig (10).
- Each customer has a known demand d_i of small packages for delivery and is associated with a predefined service time s_i equal to 5 minutes including the necessary receipt confirmation procedures.
- Each customer presents a time window (e_i, l_i) , where e_i and l_i represent the earliest and latest times during the day that service can take place.
- Vehicles must remain at the customer locations during the service, while there is a waiting time w_i if a vehicle arrives before the customer's earliest time window.
- Each customer must be visited only once by exactly one vehicle.
- The load of a vehicle must not exceed vehicle's maximum capacity at any time along its route. The maximum capacity of each vehicle is equal to $20m^3$ and the vehicles are small trucks with a detachable of $4m$.
- A routing plan should also satisfy the time window constraints for the depot (i.e., the operating hours of the transport company from 06:00 to 16:00).

For the pilot application, a shadow electric vehicle (BMW i3) was used in order to examine how efficient could be for small deliveries in an urban area utilizing the proposed technologically advanced system. The studied vehicle Fig. (11) has a range of up to 18kwh which is equivalent to about 150km.

Fig. 9: Tracking Polygon Subsystem ID = 4

Fig. 11: Electric Vehicle Used

Fig. 10: Locations of Corporate Customers

A. Technical Implementation

Fig. (12) shows the equipment used in the pilot application. It includes (i) a GPS logger which was secured at a flat point in an improvised way to ensure its stability during routing, (ii) a GPS logger magnetic antenna which was attached to the roof of the BMW i3 vehicle, and (iii) the connection of GPS logger with the OBD II Port (On Board Diagnostics) to get data from the ECU (Engine Control Unit) of the vehicle.

Fig. 12: Electric GPS logger (1), Equipment attached in the Vehicle (2), GPS logger Antenna 20 HZ (3), Connection of GPS logger with OBD II Port

B. Results of the Pilot Application

For the evaluation of the proposed technologically advanced system, the best obtained routing plan has been assessed and the two different routes of the plan were analysed and evaluated in terms of total distance traveled, average speed and mean energy consumption. The Race logger GPS data software was used to collect important data and obtain the necessary information of the studied indicators. Fig 13 and 14 present the speed map of route 1 and route 2, respectively. The trace colour changes according to the speed range, the red colour indicates that the speed is over 90 km/h, the yellow colour indicates that the speed range is 50-60km/h and the blue colour indicates that the speed is 20km/h or less.

Studying route 1, in the Thessaloniki ring road (area 1 in the map) the speed range is higher while at urban areas or villages (areas 2 in the map) it is quite low. In suburban roads and in the provincial network (areas 3 in the map) the

Fig. 13: Speed Map of Route 1

speed range remains from 50 to 60 km/h. On the other hand, in case of route 2 the speed range is lower than in route 1 since most of the served customers are located in the central area of the Thessaloniki city or in suburban areas with low-speed limits. In more detail, the 41% of speed range fluctuates from 0 to 20km/h, the 27% from 21 to 39km/h and 22% from 40 to 59km/h. Higher speeds, above 90km/h, cover a smaller percentage of the route (10%) and the average speed is 28.9km/h. The total traveled distance is equal to 54.7km and the mean energy consumption is 14.5kW / 100km. Regarding route 2, the 50% of speed range fluctuates from 0 to 20km/h, about the 30% from 21 to 39km/h and almost 14% from 40 to 59km/h. Higher speeds, above 90km/h, cover a very smaller percentage of the route (6%) and the average speed is 25.4km/h. The total traveled distance is equal to 123.9km and the mean energy consumption is 14.3kW / 100km. It is worth mentioning that the mean energy consumption is slightly lower than route 1 proving that electric vehicles are more appropriate for urban environments as low speeds, braking and deceleration favour energy recovery while high speeds consume energy at a faster rate.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we showed the deployment of a network of traffic light devices in a real world scenario. The traffic lights device, in conjunction with a vehicle subsystem comprise a wireless vehicular network for routing. In particular the vehicles subsystem transmits its GPS stigma and its speed to a server. The traffic lights device counts the vehicles that pass in front of its camera, in order to produce queues. These

Fig. 14: Speed Map of Route 2

metrics are utilised to construct a weight, which dictates the next routing option of a vehicle. We give the deployment of such devices and results that show the capturing of the vehicles, with their respective countings. Finally we present a real world application of the deployment of an electric vehicle to visit multiple customers in Thessaloniki and we obtain metrics, which will be useful for the utilisation of our vehicles' subsystem.

For our future work, we aim to utilise the OSRM towards a complete routing application by referencing the weights with the respective speeds of the vehicles. We aim to construct the routing model as a separate algorithm in the OSRM. Finally, we will use the vehicle subsystem to the real world application using the electric vehicle.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Co-financed by the European Union and Greek national funds through the Operational Program Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship and Innovation, under the call RESEARCH – CREATE - INNOVATE (project code: T1EDK-04012)

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